

THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the current types and directions of modern linguistics.

KEY WORDS

*linguistics, terminology,
sociolinguistics, static linguistics,
computer linguistics*

The history of language learning dates back centuries, with linguistics being a field of study that has been continuously evolving. The study of linguistics, or the scientific study of language and its structure, has played a crucial role in the history of language learning. From the ancient civilizations of Greece and Rome to the modern digital age, the study of how we learn and understand language has been essential for communication and cultural exchange. In ancient civilizations, language learning was often focused on the study of grammar and syntax. Scholars like Socrates and Aristotle were interested in the structure and origins of language, which laid the foundation for modern linguistics. As societies began to interact more with one another through trade and conquest, the study of languages became essential for communication and understanding between different cultures. This led to the development of language learning methods and techniques that are still used today.

In the modern era, the field of linguistics has expanded to include the study of psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and computational linguistics. With advancements in technology, language learning has become more accessible through online platforms and mobile apps. The history of language learning has shaped the way we understand and communicate with one another, and as we continue to learn and adapt, the study of linguistics will remain a crucial part of our educational journey.

The study of linguistics, or "Lingvistika" in Uzbek, has a rich and complex history dating back to ancient civilizations. Linguistics as a formal academic discipline began to take shape in the 19th century, with the work of scholars like Ferdinand de Saussure and Noam Chomsky revolutionizing the field. Throughout history, linguists have made significant contributions to our understanding of language structure, evolution, and acquisition.

One of the key turning points in the history of linguistics was the advent of structuralism in the early 20th century. Structural linguistics focused on the analysis of language as a system of

interrelated elements, rather than as a mere collection of words and rules. This approach laid the foundation for modern linguistic theory, including the study of syntax, phonetics, and semantics. Structuralism also paved the way for the development of other subfields within linguistics, such as sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, and computational linguistics.

In recent decades, linguistics has continued to evolve and expand, with the emergence of new theories and methodologies. The advent of computer technology has revolutionized the field, allowing researchers to analyze vast amounts of linguistic data and develop sophisticated computational models of language processing. As our understanding of language grows more advanced, linguistics is increasingly seen as a crucial tool for addressing pressing social issues, such as language preservation, language revitalization, and bilingual education. The history of linguistics is a testament to the enduring human fascination with language and the importance of studying its structure and evolution.

The history of the study of linguistics is the history of the search for scientific approaches to the understanding, interpretation, and analysis of meaning in speech and language. In the analysis of the historical aspect of this discourse, there are many valid questions regarding the portrayal of the local and the national according to the priority learning, concepts and views in the fields of education, science, philosophy and culture related to these fields. Another important factor in the history of the study of linguistics is the distribution of the scientific cross and paper archive of language theory, philosophy and methodology. This article examines dynamic game learning or reading and interactive approaches in distance learning, academic research, and a variety of distributed literature.

An explanation of the historical aspect of the study of linguistics in terms of cultural connections and internationalization will be an important meaning of public practice. It is necessary to analyze its meanings and views in some areas of the linguistic understanding of the educational system of the librarianship, mukhislik, academic lyceum educational responsibility systems. This will be the structure of the subject, which will take into account corporate clients, the university system and educational systems. Linguistics external warning and corporate training system still insist on studying their constructive thinking approaches in the form of sterling addresses in attracting public and foreign teachers.

With the help of studies on the type of teaching, especially on the sociological foundations of linguistics, it is necessary to study the security issues of teachers in order to strengthen the cooperative work system on the national and university systems of students and teachers of special "laboratories" and "asks" in this field. includes. OTTOMAN foPI DTM and at least a strong modern scientific and teaching community to reduce information firstly for the sake of knowledge, in general means to know the meaning of earthquake to learn in the system to form an independent teaching system of average education. The history of the study of linguistics is the history of the search for scientific approaches to the understanding, interpretation, and analysis of meaning in speech and language. In the analysis of the historical aspect of this discourse, there are many valid questions regarding the portrayal of the local and the national according to the priority learning, concepts and views in the fields of education, science, philosophy and culture related to these fields. Another important factor in the history of the study of linguistics is the distribution of the scientific cross and paper archive of language theory, philosophy and methodology. This article examines dynamic game learning or reading and interactive approaches in distance learning, academic research, and a variety of distributed literature.

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